

Master Thesis

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Performance Evaluation of High-Resolution Time-of-Flight Cameras

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Abbreviations

AMCW ...	Amplitude Modulated Continuous Wave
CCD	Charge-coupled Device
CMOS	Complementary Metal–Oxide–Semiconductor
DOE	Diffractive Optical Element
dToF	Direct Time-of-Flight
FOV	Field of View
FPN	Fixed Pattern Noise
FPS	Frames per second
ICP	Iterative Closest Point
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
PB	Pulsed-Based
PMD	Photonic Mixer Device
PoE	Power over Ethernet
LTU	Linear translation Unit
LUT	Look-up Table
MEMS	Micro-Electro-Mechanical System
MPI	Multipath Interference
NIR	Near-infrared
SBI	Suppression of Background Illumination
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SPAD	Single-Photon Avalanche Diode
ToF	Time-of-Flight
VCSEL ...	Vertical Cavity Surface Emitting Laser
VGA	Video Graphics Array

Abstract

A Time-of-Flight (ToF) camera is a 3D imaging device to perceive the range information between the ToF sensor and the scene for each camera's imaging plane pixel. It has been about 20 years since the first ToF prototype was invented based on Photonic Mixer Device (PMD) technology. With the breakthrough of ToF sensor arrays with resolutions matching the Video Graphics Array (VGA 640×480 px) and beyond in recent years, more and more high-resolution ToF cameras are pouring into the market. In this Thesis, five state-of-the-art high-resolution ToF cameras, Azure Kinect, Helios2, L515, S100D, and AD-96TOF1-EBZ, are compared via a series of experiments in terms of several key parameters, such as warm-up time, precision, lateral resolution, range resolution, and flying pixels. Some notable results are as follows: At a distance of 1m from the white panel, the distance measurement of S100D is stable with a fluctuation within 1 mm after being powered up. Azure Kinect, Helios2, and L515 can achieve precision within 2 mm in the measuring range of 0.5 to 3 m. For the point cloud of the white panel generated by L515 at a distance of 1.5m, only a small amount of flying pixel noise exists at the edge.

1 Introduction

Traditionally, 2D-imaging systems, such as charge-coupled device (CCD) cameras, present several limitations on the perception and representation of the shape and position of objects in a 3D view. In addition, it is difficult to achieve real-time conditions for traditional radar scanning due to the limitation of speed caused by point-by-point scanning. In the past few years, with the appearance of low-cost depth cameras in the market, some alternatives based on them have become popular. A depth camera provides a 2D resolution of 3D scenery to cover the distance. The number of frames acquired per time unit determines the frame rate. Due to the high frame rate of depth cameras, they have been introduced in many fields such as the mobile robotics, autonomous driving, medical imaging, etc.

The existing 3D vision technologies may be divided into three classes according to the working principles: ToF, structured light, and stereo vision. A ToF camera features an active illumination and perceives the distance by measuring the round trip of a light signal between the ToF sensor and the target object. The Amplitude Modulated Continuous Wave (AMCW) ToF camera captures the distance information by the phase difference of the emitted and the received signal. The distance of each pixel in the scene can be calculated in parallel.

Innovative research carried out by Prof. Rudolf Schwarte on the Photonic Mixer Device (PMD) in the 1990s may be considered as a core technology of ToF cameras [1]. Based on that, the single-pixel depth perception of the solid-state imaging device is realized. A ToF camera does not have the corresponding point problem based on multi-view imaging of stereo vision [2]. It also does not have the sensitivity of structured light to external light. With a larger measurement range, ToF may be implemented in a large number of applications. Due to the newness of the technology and the existing hardware limitations, ToF systems do not achieve machine precision or present inaccuracies being the main sources of error the ones inherent from intrinsic properties of the camera system and the ones derived from the measurement environment. The resolution of the ToF sensor is limited by pixel size, the sensitivity of temperature of the internal components, and the attenuation of light signal with distance. The assumption of the idealized sinusoidal signal may af-

fect the performance of the camera in different degrees at different distances. In addition, external error interference sources, such as motion artifacts caused by the low frame rate. Flying pixels, usually at the edge of an object, occur when reflected light from the foreground and background reaches the same pixel. MPI resulted in multiple reflections of light in the presence of concave or highly reflective objects.

Due to the enhancement of ToF sensor pixel resolution to VGA level, ToF imaging systems have attracted more attention within the industry over the past few years. In this Thesis, five state-of-the-art high-resolution ToF cameras will be evaluated: Azure Kinect DK, Helios2 based on the sensor of IMX556PLR from Sony, L515, S100D based on the sensor of ISOCELL Vizion 33D from Samsung and AD-96TOF1-EBZ based on the sensor of MN34906BL from Panasonic. These cameras were released after 2019. AD-96TOF1-EBZ is a PB camera, L515 is a Lidar, and the others are based on phase-shifted technology. Through a series of related experiments, we will evaluate the performance of the cameras in the following aspects: 1) The warm-up time to reach a stable state. 2) Measurement accuracy and precision at different distances. 3) and 4) Lateral and range resolution, respectively, represent the camera's minimum distinguishable distance in the lateral and radial direction. 5) Visualization of multiple parameters via sinusoidal structure. 6) Flying pixels, namely edge noise. Finally, we will summarize the performance of these high-resolution ToF cameras.

2 Related work

The error sources of the ToF camera can come from inside the system, also known as systematic errors. The errors caused by interference from the external environment are classified as non-systematic errors. It has been analyzed and summarized in some literature [3] [4].

Here, some previous works on the calibration of error sources involved in this Thesis's experiments are reviewed. In [5], Timo Kahlmann calibrated the measurement instability of the camera at the beginning of power-on by the law of warm-up time. The circular error along with the distance due to imperfect sine wave illumination is improved by Look-up Table (LUT) [5] and B-spline [6]. Compared with LUT, which stores error distance data in one pixel, B-splines are more efficient since only a few function model parameters are stored. In addition to these compensation methods during post-processing, Stephan Hussman generated a better sinusoidal signal through hardware in [7]. However, the range distance is limited due to the low power of illumination. In [8], Payne et al. adopted an alternative phase encoding approach to attenuate harmonics caused by imperfect sinusoidal illumination. The resulting worse standard deviation can be improved by lowering the duty cycle of the illumination source. Another harmonic cancellation approach was realized by Streeter and Dorrington via minor modification of the data acquisition procedure in [9]. This method has no significant effect on standard deviation. In [5], Fixed Pattern Noise (FPN) matrices are proposed to compensate for the depth error of global pixels, such as the differences in pixel depth caused by different Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor (CMOS) components, as well as amplitude-dependent errors caused by uneven light sources. At the edge of the object, the reflected light from the object and the background may be received by the same pixel, resulting in a depth error called flying pixels or jump edge points. Stefan May filtered this error according to the size of the angle, which is formed by connecting pixels with neighboring pixels and the focal point of the camera in [10].

In order to better evaluate state-of-the-art high-resolution cameras, some comparison methods and performance of the previous cameras are reviewed here. In [11] [12], SR-4000, CamCube3.0, and Kinect

v2 were verified to require at least a 30-minutes warm-up period at a distance of about 1m. D-IMager EKL-3106 only takes 15 minutes to achieve stability. The depth drift of all cameras during this period is kept above 10mm. Simone Pasinetti proved that Camboard Picoflexx requires no waiting time, and Kinect v2 shows better stability after the warm-up time of 40 min [13]. In [11]-[14], different methods were used to evaluate the accuracy and precision of multiple cameras, among which Kinect v2, SR4000, and CamCube3.0 showed better performance. The lateral and depth resolution of CamCube3.0, Kinect v1, and "Selene" module were evaluated in [15] [16]. Sarbolandi et al. conducted a comprehensive evaluation of Kinect v1 and Kinect v2 from Microsoft in [17]. While Kinect v1 is based on the structured light approach, Kinect v2 is a ToF camera. Some related evaluation work has been done on state-of-the-art high-resolution ToF cameras. In [18], Michal Tölgyessy showed the improved precision of Azure Kinect compared with Kinect v1 and v2 via the corresponding comparative experiment. In addition, the Azure Kinect is thoroughly evaluated in terms of warm-up time, accuracy, reflectivity, etc. Justin Amadeus Albert compared the performance of Azure Kinect and Kinect v2 in terms of gait analysis in [19]. Azure Kinect is proved to be more accurate regarding spatial gait parameters. In [20], three different cameras from Intel RealSense were compared, and they are based on different operating principles. The SR305 uses coded light, the D415 is based on stereo vision, and the L515 is a LiDAR camera. Through a series of comparative experiments, the L515 shows better performance in terms of failed points and accuracy.

3 The principle of 3D cameras

A 3D depth camera is an imaging device to retrieve the distance information between the camera and the scene. Benefited by the rapid growth of depth cameras in recent years, the application of 3D vision has gradually penetrated into various fields, such as 3D reconstruction, camera localization and mapping (SLAM), detection and recognition. These applications also bring more challenges to the development of depth cameras. For example, working outdoors is affected by more light noise, MPI caused by the complex environment, and the requirement to achieve longer distance and higher precision.

3.1 Time-of-Flight

3.1.1 Indirect Time-of-Flight

Indirect ToF systems may be based on Amplitude Modulated Continuous Wave (AMCW) or Pulse-Based (PB) technology. AMCW cameras calculate the distance by measuring the phase shift between emitted and received illumination period signals. Figure 1 shows the operating principle of the AMCW ToF system. The emitted signal undergoes a distance-dependent phase delay at the receiving end. In addition, the amplitude of the received signal may produce uncertain attenuation, depending on the distance between the ToF sensor and the object, the reflectivity of the object, etc.

Figure 1: Operation principle of ToF system

The mathematical representation of the original modulated light signal $s(t)$ and reflected signal $r(t)$ is:

$$s(t) = 1 + a \cdot \cos(\omega t) \quad (1)$$

$$r(t) = A \cos(\omega t - \phi) + B \quad (2)$$

where A and B are the unknown amplitude and offset of the reflected signal, respectively. ϕ is a scene-dependent phase shift, and $\omega = 2\pi f$ is the angular frequency, being f the modulation frequency. The phase shift and modulation frequency are related to the distance d as follows:

$$d = c\phi/2\omega \quad (3)$$

where c is the speed of light.

The pixel measures the cross-correlation between reflected signal $r(t)$ and the reference $s(t)$ [21], and samples at the time τ_q are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{r,s}(\tau_q) &= \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T r^*(t) s(t + \tau_q) dt \\ &= \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T [A \cos(\omega t - \phi) + B] [1 + a \cdot \cos(\omega t + \omega \tau_q)] dt \\ &= \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T [A a \cos(\omega t - \phi) \cos(\omega t + \omega \tau_q) + B] dt \\ &= \frac{Aa}{2} \cos(\omega \tau_q + \phi) + B \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

With the help of “four-bucket” sampling [3], namely, $\tau_q = \pi q/2\omega$ with $q = 0, \dots, 3$. the amplitude A , the phase shift ϕ and the offset B of the single-pixel measurement are obtained as:

$$A = \sqrt{(C(\tau_3) - C(\tau_1))^2 + (C(\tau_0) - C(\tau_2))^2} / 2a \quad (5)$$

$$\phi = \arctan \left[\frac{C(\tau_3) - C(\tau_1)}{C(\tau_0) - C(\tau_2)} \right] \quad (6)$$

$$B = \frac{C(\tau_0) + C(\tau_1) + C(\tau_2) + C(\tau_3)}{4} \quad (7)$$

Even in the case of square demodulation signals, equivalent equations for retrieving the amplitude and the phase shift hold, provided that the illumination signal is perfectly sinusoidal. Within the sampling interval, the number of accumulated electrons generated by photoelectric conversion is measured, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The sample process of the incident AMCW signal

It is observed that C1-C4 are four control signals with the same sampling interval, and their corresponding phase offsets are 0 , π , $\pi/2$, and $3\pi/2$, respectively. By measuring the number of electrons Q_1 - Q_4 , which are accumulated in the corresponding interval, the amplitude A , the phase shift ϕ , and the offset B can be obtained as:

$$A = \sqrt{(Q_1 - Q_2)^2 + (Q_3 - Q_4)^2} / 2 \quad (8)$$

$$\phi = \arctan \left[\frac{Q_3 - Q_4}{Q_1 - Q_2} \right] \quad (9)$$

$$B = \frac{Q_1 + Q_2 + Q_3 + Q_4}{4} \quad (10)$$

Since the phase has a periodicity of 2π , for the AMCW cameras, an ambiguity caused by phase wrap will appear when the measurement distance exceeds half of the wavelength. Then the maximum non-ambiguous range is defined as:

$$d_{max} = \frac{c}{2f} \quad (11)$$

With the multi-frequency techniques, the non-ambiguous range is extended by high frequency without damaging high precision. If two different frequencies f_1 and f_2 are considered, the non-ambiguous range is extended to [22]:

$$R = \frac{c}{2 \cdot (f_1 - f_2)} \quad (12)$$

where c is the light velocity and $f_1 - f_2$ is the beat frequency, i.e., the frequency at which the two modulations agree. With the “phase unwrapping” techniques based on multi-frequency, the true position of objects can be calculated.

As for the pulse-based camera, an emitted short light pulse is reflected in the scene and again captured by a sensor array. The sensor uses two non-overlapping controls signals C1 and C2, for electronic shuttering. The two controls signals own the same period as the pulse signal, as shown in Figure 3. According to integrating photoelectrons Q_1 and Q_2 from the reflected light at the shutter window, the distance between the camera and the scene is calculated as:

$$d = \frac{1}{2}c\Delta t \left(\frac{Q_2}{Q_1 + Q_2} \right) \quad (13)$$

Figure 3: Sample process of the incident pulsed signal

3.1.2 Direct Time-of-Flight

Another way to measure the distance from pulse-based ToF sensor is via a fast photodetector, usually, a Single-Photon Avalanche Diode (SPAD). It can direct the duration of pulse from emission to reception. This principle is also called direct Time-of-Flight (dToF). A mathematical representation is

$$d = \frac{ct}{2} \quad (14)$$

where c is the speed of light, and t is the flight duration between the sensor and the scene. The working principle of LiDAR is the same as dToF. Based on the difference in steering systems, there are currently two main types of LiDAR cameras on the market. The first one is the flash LiDAR camera. It features the Vertical Cavity Surface Emitting Laser (VCSEL) and Diffractive Optical Element (DOE) to allow the sensor to emit laser beams in multiple directions [23], such as the LiDAR module from Apple iPad Pro [24]. The second type of LiDAR uses the Micro-Electro-Mechanical System (MEMS) mirror scanning technology, which achieves the 3D scanning and receiving information by constantly rotating the transmitter. Figure 4 shows a part of laser spots based on MEMS mirror scanning technology from L515.

Figure 4: Micro-Electromechanical System (MEMS) mirror scanning of L515 [25]

3.2 Stereo vision

Stereo vision obtains 3D imaging via exploiting different perspectives from multiple cameras or a moving camera. One of the most popular schemes in the current market is binocular vision. It consists of two cameras separated by a distance similar to the human eye and satisfying that their field of view (FOV) overlaps at the desired distance from the observed object.

The depth measurement principle of stereo vision is shown in Figure 5. The distance between the two cameras B , called the baseline, is a known parameter. O_R and O_T are the origins of each camera's coordinate system, respectively. In the world coordinate system, which is defined as an inertial reference system fixed at an arbitrary position, p and p' are the corresponding points generated on the imaging plane for the same point P in space. f is the focal length of the camera, x is the half size of the image plane, and $x_R - x_T$ is the disparity obtained by the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} D_{\text{dis}} &= (x_R - x) + (x - x_T) \\ &= x_R - x_T \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Figure 5: Depth imaging principle of binocular vision [26]

Since the similar triangles, $\triangle PO_R O_T$ and $\triangle Ppp'$ are proportional, the depth from object to cameras Z can be calculated as follows:

$$\frac{B}{Z} = \frac{B - D_{\text{dis}}}{Z - f} \quad (16)$$

$$Z = \frac{Bf}{D_{\text{dis}}} \quad (17)$$

3.3 Structured light

Different from stereo vision, the structured light system replaces one of the observation cameras with a projector. The projector illuminates a pattern (spots, stripes, etc.) distorted by the non-planar scene. According to the distortion, which is acquired by the image sensor, the estimation of depth information can be achieved [27]. In contrast to stereoscopic vision, structured light does not require complex algorithms to solve the corresponding points problem since the pattern is fixed at the pixel position of the imager. The typical configuration of a structured light system is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Depth imaging principle with a spot projector of structured light

The base distance b and the angle α are determined via the initial calibration of the structured light system. The angle β is dependent on the position of the object. Based on triangulation, the relation is obtained as follows:

$$\frac{d}{\sin\alpha} = \frac{b}{\sin\gamma} \quad (18)$$

From $\gamma = \pi - (\alpha + \beta)$, then the distance d can be calculated:

$$d = \frac{b \cdot \sin\alpha}{\sin(\alpha + \beta)} \quad (19)$$

3.4 Comparison of the 3D imaging technologies

Table 1 shows the main parameters of Time-of-Flight, stereo vision, and structured light imaging system. The advantage of ToF cameras lies in their simple algorithm and larger measurement range. Stereo vision is more advantageous outdoors, and the structured light system provides accurate depth imaging over short distances.

Parameter	Time-of-Flight	Stereo vision	Structured light
Active illumination	yes	no	yes
Software complexity	low	high	medium
Multipath interference	yes	no	no
Low-light performance	good	weak	good
Outdoor performance	medium	good	weak
Latency	low	medium	medium
Maximum range	long	mid	short
Resolution	medium	medium	high
Power consumption	medium on camera low on processor	low on camera high on processor	medium on camera high on processor
Alignment	no	yes	yes
Size	small	limited by baseline	limited by baseline

Table 1: 3D technology comparison

3.5 Measurements errors of ToF camera

Due to the novelty of ToF technology and hardware limitations, several error sources are present during signal acquisition and processing. They can be divided into two categories: systematic errors and non-systematic errors. The systematic errors mainly come from intrinsic properties and imaging conditions of the camera system. In contrast, the non-systematic errors are related to the external environment.

3.5.1 Systematic Errors

Wiggling Error In some cases, a perfect sinusoidal signal can not be generated as an emitted signal, yielding a wiggling error. It is a distance measurement error along with the working range of the camera. Since the demodulation process is based on harmonic sinusoidal signals, the imperfect sinusoidal waveform may yield errors during the computation of the distance information. This error is also called circular error due to the sinusoidal form of this error in the distance domain.

Built-in pixel-related errors CCD technology has only one or several output nodes to reach the charge-voltage conversion, so its voltage output is uniform. In CMOS technology, this process is conducted parallel in every pixel. It requires a narrower bandwidth of the charge amplifier than the one employed by CCDs to achieve low power consumption. However, it leads to higher fixed noise due to nonuniform charge-voltage conversion.

Amplitude-related errors Systematic non-uniform near-infrared (NIR) LEDs illumination leads to non-negligible light variations between the center and boundaries of the sensor array. Since the depth accuracy is highly related to the amplitude of the incident light, an overestimation of the depth may appear in the external boundaries of the images [3].

Temperature-related errors Semiconductor elements are sensitive to temperature magnitude and fluctuations. The increase of the operating temperatures for CCD and CMOS results from the self-induced heating caused by thermal losses of the camera electronic components and external temperature changes. The rise in temperature leads to an increase in the vibration of electrons, thus producing more noise. This may lead to performance degradation in determining depth information from the evaluated scene.

3.5.2 Non-systematic Errors

Multipath Interference is a common scene-dependent error source for all ToF cameras. For some complex, especially concave objects, as shown in Figure 7, the modulated light is reflected multiple times across the surface. This results in some pixels cells receiving the echoes of the optical signals from different paths. Since these paths contain different phase information, the depth calculation of a sensor pixel is the weighted average distances based on these paths yielding an overestimation of distance.

Figure 7: MPI phenomenon

Flying pixel noise is a particular form of MPI. When the light beam from the same pixel hits the edge of an object, it may be divided and reflected by the object and the background, respectively. As a result, the sensor picks up a superposition of the signals from object

and background reflections, leading to incorrect depth estimation. Figure 8 shows a point cloud of a white panel acquired at the distance of 1500 mm using Helios2. It is observed that some flying pixel noise appears at the edge of the whiteboard.

Figure 8: 3D point cloud for a white panel placed at a distance of 1500 mm from the camera.

Light scattering Light scattering is caused by multiple reflections of incident light between the lens and the sensor [28]. Weak signals from distant objects (the background) are more susceptible to scattering by strong incident lights reflected by objects in the foreground, resulting in an underestimation of the depth of distant objects. In addition, the closer the objects are, the greater the light scattering errors may be.

Motion artifacts In 3D imaging, the relative motion between the sensor and the object leads to motion artifacts. As described in section 3.1.1, the depth calculation performed by the ToF camera is based on the four-phase algorithm. During the relative movement between sensors and objects, the phase shift observed at the corresponding sensor pixel changes over the integration time, yielding depth estimation bias [29].

4 ToF cameras

At the end of the 20th century, Professor Rudolf Schwarte succeeded in the research of Photonic Mixer Device (PMD) [1]. It became the core semiconductor device in ToF pixel to realize fast optical sensing and acquisition of phase information. Soon afterwards, the first ToF prototype was invented based on PMD technology, as shown in Figure 9(a) [21]. Since then, the progressive development and the implementation of new concepts have never been interrupted. This section will briefly present the evolution of ToF systems and a detailed description of the state-of-the-art high-resolution ToF cameras evaluated in this Thesis.

4.1 Evolution of ToF imaging systems

PMD Technologies was founded in 2002 and is named after their core technology. Their initial product PMDTec 3k-S was featured with suppression of background illumination (SBI) technology to suppress external light noise. PMD released a good performance phase-shifted ToF camera, Camcube 3.0, in 2010, as shown in Figure 9(e), which is well known to ToF camera researchers. This camera features a high depth pixel array of 200×200 px and a long measurement range of 7.5 m. In 2015, the first consumer ToF camera of PMD Camboard Picoflexx was launched. It can be better integrated into mobile devices due to its low form factor and low weight. The Selene Module with the small size is shown in Figure 9(k), and it has been used in some articles for material identification [30] and dirt evaluation [16].

In 2004, Canesta launched their first ToF camera, DP200, as shown in Figure 9(b), which features a maximum FOV of $70^\circ \times 70^\circ$ and a frame rate of 30 FPS. This company was later acquired by Microsoft in 2010. In the same year, Microsoft launched Kinect for Xbox 360, mainly used for 3D perception in games, such as gesture recognition and body skeleton detection. The low cost and high performance caught the attention of scientists and robotics enthusiasts, which increased the field of application to object recognition, SLAM, and others. Soon afterwards, Microsoft released Kinect v1 and v2 for commercial use. Kinect v1 is based on the structure light technology of PrimeSense. Kinect v2 is a phase-shifted ToF camera,

which contains a worldwide-highest lateral resolution sensor array of 512×424 pixels at the time. Additionally, Microsoft's latest release, Azure Kinect DK, will be covered in more details later.

Mesa Imaging released two AMCW ToF cameras, SR3000 and SR4000, in 2006 and 2008, respectively. Compared with SR3000, the main performance improvement of SR4000 is the internal reference path, which realizes internal synchronization between illumination and sensor. Another improvement is a more stable passive cooling system [31]. SR4000 features an image sensor pixel of 176×144 px and two different measurement ranges of 5 and 10 m, depending on the camera system. In 2014, Mesa Imaging was bought by Heptagon. Additionally, it was later acquired by ams AG in 2017.

Softkinect launched two ToF cameras in 2012, DS311 and DS325, as shown in Figure 9(g)(h). Comparatively speaking, DS315 features larger measurement distance of 5 m, and DS325 has a higher resolution of 320×240 px and an FOV of $74^\circ \times 58^\circ$, which is more suitable for close measurement. In 2015, Sony announced the acquisition of Softkinect. In 2017, they developed a small ToF camera, DS541, which is suitable for integration into mobile devices. Their latest VGA ToF sensor IMX556PLR has attracted some modular manufacturers, which will be introduced later.

Figure 9: Development history of ToF cameras (Reference of pictures: (a) [21], (b, c) [32], (d, e) [11], (f) [33], (g, h) [23])

4.2 State-of-the-art high-resolution ToF cameras

4.2.1 Azure Kinect DK

Microsoft launched Azure Kinect DK in 2019, which is presented in Figure 10. This Time-of-Flight camera is primarily focused on enterprise users and artificial intelligence usage. For example, monitoring patient movements through bone tracking to prevent potential accidents or injuries.

Figure 10: Azure Kinect DK

In order to understand the performance improvement of Azure Kinect's depth camera over the previous two cameras, a comparison of their main parameters is presented in Table 2. It must be noted that Azure Kinect supports four different depth modes. The WFOV and NFOV refer to a wide field of view of $120^\circ \times 120^\circ$ and a narrow field of view of $75^\circ \times 65^\circ$, respectively. They are realized via two NIR Laser diodes. The resolution of binned mode is reduced to a quarter compared to unbinned mode. A more stable pixel is generated by four adjacent pixels, which can improve precision and extend the measurement range. Except for the NFOV binned mode, the lateral resolution of all modes has been improved on Kinect v1 and v2. Furthermore, in WFOV unbinned mode, the lateral resolution can reach up to 1-Megapixel, and the measurement range is extended to 5.46 m under the mode of NFOV binned.

Mode	Resolution	Field of View	Frame Rate	Measurement range(m)	exposure time(ms)
NFOV unbinned	640 × 576	75° × 65°	0,5,15,30	0.5-3.86	12.8
NFOV 2 × 2 binned	320 × 288	75° × 65°	0,5,15,30	0.5-5.46	12.8
WFOV 2 × 2 binned	512 × 512	120° × 120°	0,5,15,30	0.25-2.88	12.8
WFOV unbinned	1024 × 1024	120° × 120°	0,5,15	0.5-2.21	20.3
Kinect v1	320 × 240	57° × 43°	30	0.4-4	auto
Kinect v2	512 × 424	70° × 60°	30	0.5-4.5	auto

Table 2: Specification of different depth camera modes [34]

In addition to the depth camera, Azure Kinect also features a color camera, an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), and a microphone array. The color camera features a high-resolution array of up to 4096×3072 pixels. Furthermore, Azure Kinect supports the generation of color point clouds, facilitating visualization or classification of the point cloud. An IMU is used to measure the angular rate and acceleration of the cameras. It permits the implementation of autonomous navigation systems.

For more detailed parameters of Azure Kinect and other state-of-the-art high-resolution ToF cameras, please refer to Table 3.

camera	Azure kinect DK	Helios2	L515	S100D	AD-96TOF1-EBZ
Release date	2019	2020	2019	2019	2020
Supply	Microsoft	LUCID Vision Labs	Intel	Meerecompany CubeEye	Analog Devices
Sensor model	Microsoft	Sony IMX556PLR	Intel	Samsung ISOCELL Vizion 33D	Panasonic MN34906BL
Working principle	Phase shift	Phase shift	LiDAR	Phase shift	Pulsed
Lateral resolution(px)	Table 2	640 × 480	Table 5	640 × 480	640 × 480
Pixel size	3.5μm×3.5μm	10μm×10μm	n.a.	7μm×7μm	n.a.
RGB camera	yes	no	yes	no	no
Measurement range(m)	0.25-5.46	0.3-8.33	0.25-9	0.2-4	0.25-6
Field of View	Table 2	69° × 51°	75° × 55°	60° × 45°	90° × 69.2°
Frame Rate(FPS)	Table 2	30	30	30	30
Exposure time	Table 2	62.5,250, 1000μs	< 100ns, per depth point	n.a.	n.a.
IMU	yes	no	yes	no	no
Number of illumination sources	2	4	1	1	4
Power Consumption(W)	<5.9W	P _{ave} <12W	<3.5W	1.5 W	<20W
Dimension(mm)	103 × 39 ×126	60 × 60 ×77.5	(Diameter×height) 61×26	60 × 15 ×69	n.a.
Weight(g)	440	398	95	4.9	n.a.
Operating Temperature(°C)	10-25	-10-60	0-30	-15-50	-20-85
Price	\$399	\$1495	\$349	\$535	\$735
Operating system	Windows 10, Linux	Windows8/10 Linux	Windows, Linux	Windows Ubuntu	Windows Linux,Mac

Table 3: Specification comparison of the high-resolution ToF cameras considered in this work

4.2.2 Helios2

In 2018, Sony released the high-performance IMX556PLR sensor. This sensor combined SoftKinetic’s ToF technology with its own backside-illuminated (BSI) technology, which increases the light gathering efficiency of the sensor and decreases noise. Additionally, the pixel array of this sensor achieves 640×480 pixels.

In 2019, LUCID Vision Labs incorporated the sensor into its Helios ToF camera. Besides, some other companies have also shown their interest in this sensor. For example, Basler also deployed the IMX556PLR in its blaze ToF camera [35], and Seeed Technology based its DepthEye Turbo ToF camera around it as well [36].

In 2020, LUCID Vision Labs announced the next generation for their ToF cameras Helios2, as shown in Figure 11(a). Helios2 improves the precision to the previous generation yielding sub-millimeter level. Furthermore, the distance modes are extended to six, as presented in Table 4.

Distance mode	1.25mMode	3mMode	4mMode	5mMode	6mMode	8.3mMode
Accuracy	$\pm 4mm$	$\pm 10mm$	$\pm 10mm + 0.25\%$ of depth	$\pm 4mm + 0.1\%$ of depth	$\pm 10mm + 0.5\%$ of depth	$\pm 4mm + 0.2\%$ of depth

Table 4: Accuracy of Helios2 in different modes [37]

As it is observed in Table 4, Helios2 achieves high accuracy for the distance modes of 5 m and 8.3 m, because the two modes adopt multiple frequencies 120 MHz+90 MHz and 90 MHz+72 MHz, respectively. Dual frequency technology can extend the short non-ambiguous range of high frequencies while ensuring high accuracy, which we have discussed in section 3.1.1.

Helios2 is featured with 4 VCSEL laser diodes presented in Figure 11(a). They provide stronger illumination for long-distance measurement and yield a larger field of view. Helios2 is equipped with an M12 port and supports Power over Ethernet (PoE), e.g., the data and power can be transmitted via one ethernet cable, as shown in Figure 11(b). Here we will use a PoE injector to provide power for data transmission.

(a) Helios2

(b) Helios2 with M12 cable and PoE injector

Figure 11: Helios2

4.2.3 L515

Over the past decades, semiconductor supplier Intel has been making significant efforts in leading-edge technologies, such as computer vision. In late 2019, Intel expanded its RealSense product line by introducing the Lidar camera L515, as shown in Figure 12. L515 is featured with a small form factor of 61×26 mm (diameter \times height). It enables a high pixel account of 1024×768 pixels at 30 FPS due to the low exposure time of $t_{\text{exp}} < 100$ ns per depth point and short photon-to-depth latency of 4 ms [38]. L515 supports two other depth modes, as presented in Table 5.

Like Azure Kinect, the L515 is also equipped with a color camera, with a lateral resolution of 1920×1680 and an IMU. Besides, this camera is affordable and uses a proprietary MEMS mirror scanning technology, enabling better laser power efficiency (less than 3.5 W).

Figure 12: L515

Depth Resolution	Range at 15% reflectivity	Range at 95% reflectivity
QVGA(320 × 240)	0.25-3.9m	0.25-9m
VGA(640 × 480)	0.25-3.9m	0.25-9m
XGA(1024 × 768)	0.25-2.6m	0.25-6.5m

Table 5: Different modes of L515 [38]

4.2.4 S100D

In 2019, Cube Eye of Meerecompany released a compact design ToF evaluation board, S100D, which features Samsung’s first ToF sensor ISOCELL Vizion 33D. The S100D possesses a dimension of $60 \times 15 \times 9$ mm, as shown in Figure 13, and lower power consumption than the L515, of only 1.5 W. Besides, the lateral resolution achieves the level of VGA (640 × 480 pixels).

Figure 13: S100D

4.2.5 AD-96TOF1-EBZ

The AD-96TOF1-EBZ, launched by Analog Devices in 2020, is a depth imaging hardware platform. It requires an additional processor board to perform 3D development. As shown in Figure 14, the processor board, DragonBoard 410c, is located at the back of the camera. The front two plates of the camera are components of AD-96TOF1-EBZ, which consists of a Laser Transmitter Board and the Analog Front End (AFE) mezzanine board [39]. Similar to Helios2, AD-96TOF1-EBZ is equipped with 4 individual lasers in the Laser Transmitter Board. AFE mezzanine board contains a Panasonic ToF sensor MN34906BL with a high-resolution sensor array of 640×480 pixels.

Figure 14: AD-96TOF1-EBZ with DragonBoard 410c

5 Experiments and Results

In this section, several important parameters of the cameras will be evaluated through a series of targeted experimental settings, and the most significant results will be discussed. All the cameras are mounted on a linear translation unit (LTU), which features a positioning accuracy better than 1 mm, as shown in Figure 15(a). We use a bracket to realize the free rotation of the cameras, as presented in Figure 15(b). In addition, a white panel with a side length of 1 m is placed at the end of LTU. This white panel is made of aluminum coated with Barium Sulfate, which is a perfect Lambertian reflector.

(a) Linear translation Unit

(b) Azure Kinect mounted on the bracket

Figure 15: Set up of experiment

Since the pixel array is more likely to reach saturation when receiving the reflected light signal through the material with high reflectivity. The measured distance may be affected by gross errors. In order to reduce this interference from the external environment during the acquisition, these materials were covered as much as possible with paper or dark cloth.

Besides, we blocked all the glass windows in the room and turned off all the light sources in the room to reduce external noise. According to the Gaussian assumption, the standard deviation of the range measurement affected by ambient light can be derived from the following equation [40]:

$$\sigma = \frac{c}{4\pi\sqrt{2}f_{\text{mod}}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{B + A_{\text{sig}}}}{c_{\text{demod}}A_{\text{sig}}} \quad (20)$$

where c is the light velocity and f_{mod} is the modulation frequency. A_{sig} and offset B are the mean number of electrons generated by the signal component and the background illumination, respectively. The demodulation contrast c_{demod} is equal to the ratio between the Amplitude A and A_{sig} :

$$c_{\text{demod}} = \frac{A}{A_{\text{sig}}} \quad (21)$$

Therefore, reducing the background light as much as possible contributes to acquiring more accurate data.

On the other hand, we also need to ensure the accurate placement of the camera. The first step is to orient the camera and ensure its depth imaging plane is parallel to the whiteboard. In this step, we use the real-time observation software dedicated to each camera for coarse adjustment. For fine adjustment, the averaged depth map of 100 frames is observed to ensure no significant deviation around the white panel. Then the depth imaging plane of the camera is sufficiently parallel to the whiteboard. Step two, we also need to adjust the distance between the camera and the white panel. Since we could not accurately determine the origin of each camera's depth coordinate system, it is impossible to realize precise positioning based on a high-precision laser. Another method is to find the reference positions of each camera at different distances by relying on the high accuracy of LTU. First, we used a high-precision laser to roughly position the camera 1 m away from the white panel. The choice of 1 m distance is due to the more accurate performance of the camera at close range. The center 20×20 pixels of averaged 100 frames depth data are extracted for the calculation of the distance. The position of the camera is adjusted until the distance error is less than 2 mm, and this adjusted position is taken as the reference position of 1 m. Other reference positions can be directly obtained by the high precision of LTU.

It is worth noting that the depth camera of Azure Kinect is tilted down by 6 degrees compared with its color camera, as shown in Figure 16. It means that when Azure Kinect is leveled and is pointing

orthogonally at the white panel, the correct depth map can be observed after being transformed to the coordinate system of the color camera. Another method is to adjust the camera so that it tilts upward by 6 degrees from the horizontal direction. This method is adopted in our experiment, as shown in the figure 15(b).

Figure 16: Azure Kinect DK coordinate systems [41]

After the adjustment, the depth maps averaged by 100 frames from all cameras are generated in Figure 17. It is observed that there is no obvious deviation of depth information at the edge of the panel caused by camera tilt. Furthermore, Figures 17(a), (b), and (c) show Z-plane depth maps of the white panel, which are captured by Azure Kinect, Helios2, and L515, respectively. Among them, most pixels of the Z-plane maps imaged by Azure Kinect and Helios2 show a depth range within 10 mm. However, S100D and AD-96TOF1-EBZ show depth maps, which are defined as the distance between each point on the whiteboard and the origin of the depth coordinate system, as shown in Figures 17 (d) and (e). In the two depth maps, the depth differences between the edge and center of the white panel are 200 and 400 mm, respectively.

A compensation method is defined here to achieve the transformation of depth map to Z-plane map. It is defined as the error between the reference and measurement distance at each pixel of the camera. The reference distance of each position is determined based on the previous camera adjustments and the high-precision LTU. That is to say, we only need to adjust the camera at 1 m and take this position as the reference distance of 1m. Other reference distances can be obtained by the movement of LTU from 0.5 meters to 3 meters in the steps of 10 cm. The measurement data is calculated by aver-

aging 100 frames of depth maps at each position. Figure 18 shows the visualization of the compensation matrix at the distance of 1000 mm using S100D and the Z-plane depth map after calibration by the compensation matrix.

(a) Z-plane depth map of Azure Kinect

(b) Z-plane depth map of Helios2

(c) Z-plane depth map of L515

(d) Depth map of S100D

(e) Depth map of AD-96TOF1-EBZ

Figure 17: Depth maps of white panel averaged by 100 frames at the distance of 1000 mm

Figure 18: Calibrate the depth map of S100D via compensation matrix at distance of 1000 mm

Data acquisition for all cameras is carried out on the same computer. Except for L515, which is controlled by Matlab, the other cameras are run in a C++ environment. Using the MEX function, the C++ data can be directly converted to the Matlab environment. All data post-processing is carried out in Matlab.

5.1 Warm-up

In the first few minutes after a ToF camera is turned on, the internal temperature may rise due to the heat loss of the camera's electronic components, and then it should finally stabilize. Because of the temperature-related errors, the temperature variation of the ToF camera will affect its distance measurement precision.

In this section, an experiment was devised to determine the warm-up period of every camera. As shown in Figure 15(a), the distance between the camera and the white panel is 1 m. Furthermore, all cameras are powered off for at least two hours to completely cool down. To ensure that the camera does not cool down during the acquisition process, all cameras were operated in continuous mode. AD-96TOF1-EBZ can capture about 13 FPS as a result of USB connection limitations [42], and all other cameras can achieve 30 FPS in this mode.

In this experiment, a frame is stored every 10 seconds, and other

frames are discarded. The whole experiment lasts for 2 hours, totaling 720 frames per data set. The mean value of a central 20×20 pixels of each captured frame is calculated as the distance information. The NFOV unbinned mode of Azure Kinect and 5 m distance mode of Helios2 are adopted during this test. In addition, the integration time of Helios2 is set to $1000 \mu\text{s}$. The results are shown as follows:

Figure 19: Warm up test of Azure Kinect at the distance of 1 m

Figure 20: Warm up test of Helios2 at the distance of 1 m

(a) Distance variation

(b) Histogram of distances

Figure 21: Warm up test of L515 at the distance of 1 m

(a) Distance variation

(b) Histogram of distances

Figure 22: Warm up test of S100D at the distance of 1 m

(a) Distance variation

(b) Histogram of distances

Figure 23: Warm up test of AD-96TOF1-EBZ at the distance of 1 m

In Figure 19(a), Azure Kinect shows a slight depth drift of about 1 mm at the beginning of the measurement. The depth measurement tends to be stable after 35 minutes, and the fluctuation is kept within 0.5 mm.

Compared with Azure Kinect, Helios2 needs a more extended warm-up period of approximately 50 min to achieve good measurement stability. Besides, it has a slightly larger initial depth error of about 2 mm, as shown in Figure 20(a). After stabilizing, Helios2 shows the smallest depth value fluctuation within 0.4 mm among all cameras. The warm-up period of L515 lasts at least 40 min. During this time, the depth values decrease by 10 mm. After the warm-up phase, the variation range of the final depth value is as high as 5 mm, as shown in Figure 21(a).

Different from other cameras, S100D does not have temperature-related errors. As shown in Figure 22, there is no obvious depth drift in the whole time zone. Furthermore, the fluctuation of depth value is also kept within a small range of 1 mm. The reasons may be as follows: firstly, S100D is an evaluation board, which dissipates heat better than other cameras with a shell. Secondly, the low power consumption of 1.5W generates less heat [43].

AD-96TOF1-EBZ shows a similar warm-up period and fluctuation of stable state to L515 in Figure 23(a). Nevertheless, the depth drift is 4 mm less than the 10 mm of L515. Although AD-96TOF1-EBZ is also an evaluation board, its maximum power consumption of 20 W is much higher than 1.5 W of S100D [44], generating more heat. The experimental results show that all cameras except S100D exhibit depth information drift caused by temperature-related errors after being powered up. For the sake of avoiding these errors for the following experiments, the waiting of the corresponding warm-up period is performed in advance.

5.2 Accuracy and precision

Accuracy and precision are two significant parameters to evaluate the performance of the ToF camera. Among them, accuracy refers to the difference between the mean measured value and the real value. It represents the maximum systematic error on the distance measurement. The precision is characterized by the spread of mea-

surement values around the mean value.

The attenuation of light intensity is inversely proportional to the square of the distance, which leads to worse accuracy with the increase of distance. For an AMCW range finder, the standard deviation of the range measurement σ is approximately linearly related to the distance R [45]:

$$\sigma \propto \sqrt{\frac{\lambda R^2}{\rho \cos \alpha}} \quad (22)$$

where λ is the signal wavelength, ρ and α are the object reflectivity and the angle of incidence, respectively.

Apart from this, the accuracy of distance measurement is also affected by the wiggling error along with the distance, which is discussed in section 3.5.1.

In this experiment, the accuracy and precision of every camera at different distances are evaluated. To present the best performance of the cameras, some different modes of the same cameras are evaluated as well. First, the camera is adjusted at 1 m in the way discussed before. Since the exact position of each depth coordinate system's origin can not be determined, it is impossible to determine the precise distance between the camera and the whiteboard. We assume that measured depth information at a one-meter distance is correct. With the high-precision LTU, the reference distance of every position can be obtained. Therefore, the variation of the accuracy can be obtained with varying distances.

The distance between the camera and the white panel is kept between 0.5 and 3m, and the spacing is 10 cm. 30 depth maps are acquired at each position, and the average value is taken. The mean value of a central 20×20 pixels of each averaged frame is calculated as measurement distance at different positions. For precision, we calculated the standard deviation of each pixel of the extracted central 20×20 pixels based on the acquired 30 depth frames. An average of 400-pixel results is calculated as precision. The results are shown as follows:

Figure 24: Accuracy and precision of Azure Kinect with the varying distances

In Figure 24(a), four different modes of Azure Kinect are compared. Every mode features good performance in terms of accuracy, and the error range is kept within 4 mm. It is remarkable that WFOV unbinned and WFOV binned mode feature the official measurement ranges of 2.21 m and 2.88 m, respectively, as shown in Table 2. However, they maintain a very accurate distance measurement within 3 m. Besides, the accuracy variation of the two wide modes exhibits very similar trends with varying distances.

NFOV binned mode of Azure Kinect possesses high measurement precision. Its standard deviation is always kept below 1 mm in the 3m range, as shown in Figure 24(b). NFOV unbinned mode and WFOV binned modes have very similar precision changes. Furthermore, the precision of all modes shows an approximate linear growth form with distance.

Figure 25: Accuracy and precision of Helios2 with the varying distances

During the experiment for Helios2, $250 \mu\text{s}$ exposure time is adopted in the range of 50 cm to 90 cm. For all other distances, 1000 μs exposure time is chosen. As we discussed before, the 3 m mode of Helios2 adopts a single modulation frequency of 50 MHz, and the 5 m mode features two modulation frequencies of 120 MHz and 90 MHz. The dual-frequency mode extends the non-ambiguous range compared with the single frequency of 120 MHz and improves the precision compared with the single frequency of 50 MHz. The results shown in Figure 25 are in line with our expectations. With the advantage of double frequencies, the variation range of the accuracy is reduced from 14 mm to 6 mm, and the maximum standard deviation at the distance of 2.9 m is reduced from 5 mm to 2 mm.

Figure 26: Accuracy and precision of L515 with the varying distances

Figure 27: Accuracy and precision of S100D with the varying distances

Compared with the previous two cameras, the performance of the L515 is also excellent, as shown in Figure 26. Within a distance of 2.2 m, L515 presents an accuracy change range of about 2 mm, and the accuracy variation increases to a maximum of 4 mm with the increase of distance. In terms of precision, the L515 has outstanding performance, similar to the 5 m mode of Helios2.

The accuracy change of S100D presents an approximate form of oscillation with the increase of distance, as shown in Figure 27(a), and the oscillation range is within 9 mm. As the distance increases, the standard deviation increases from a minimum of 0.8 mm at 0.7 m to 2.7 mm at 2.9 m.

Figure 28: Accuracy and precision of AD-96TOF1-EBZ with the varying distances

Figure 29: Accuracy and precision of AD-96TOF1-EBZ with the varying distances after compensation

The medium distance mode of AD-96TOF1-EBZ was adopted in this experiment. Since the medium mode can not present all effective depth pixels at 50 cm, the near mode will be used at this distance. Compared with other cameras, AD-96TOF1-EBZ shows great differences, as presented in Figure 28. In the range between 0.5 m and 1.8 m, the accuracy variation can be kept within 2% of the distance. However, when the distance exceeds this limit, the change of accuracy will increase exponentially over 30 cm, and a downward trend appears at 2.75 m.

The precision of AD-96TOF1-EBZ is presented in Figure 28(b). At a position of 50cm away from the whiteboard, a large standard de-

viation of 15 mm is presented. It is probably due to the instability of near mode relative to medium mode. After that, the standard deviation varies between 3 mm and 20 mm.

Due to the significant error in the distance measurement of this camera, especially after the distance exceeds 1.8m, the compensation matrix, which is defined at the beginning of this section, is used to correct the depth measurement. The results are shown in Figure 29. It is observed that the accuracy variation range is greatly improved by less than 8 mm. Nevertheless, nothing changes in terms of precision. Since the compensation matrix is fixed at each position, then the precision is not be affected.

5.3 Lateral resolution

The test object shown in Figure 30 is a Böhler star. It is designed to determine the lateral resolution of a depth imaging sensor [46]. This Böhler star is made of 24 alternating sectors and has a diameter of 20 cm. Based on the difference in height between the front plate and the bottom plate, the sensor will receive reflections from both plates. The better the lateral resolution of the camera is, the more apparent depth difference near the center can be recognized.

Figure 30: Böhler star

The lateral resolution r of a sensor can be calculated as:

$$r = \frac{\pi d M}{n} \quad (23)$$

where n means the number of alternating sectors of the star, d is the ratio between the diameter of the center ambiguous circle and the diameter M of the star. In case that the determination of lateral and distance information is known, the angular resolution can be easily obtained according to the trigonometric function:

$$r_{an} = \arctan \frac{r}{d} \quad (24)$$

In this experiment, the NFOV unbinned mode of Azure Kinect and the 5 m distance mode of Helios2 are adopted. The distance between the camera and the Böhler star is kept from 0.5 m to 3 m, and the step size is 10 cm. 30 frames are acquired at each position, and their average depth maps are shown in Figures 31. It is observed that all cameras show a small ambiguous circle in the center when the distance is less than or equal to 1 m. Remarkably, the Helios2 featured with two modulation frequencies exhibits excellent performance at long distances, as shown in Figure 31(g) and Figure 31(h). Azure Kinect and S100D show ambiguous circles of similar size at different positions. However, L1515 and AD-96TOF1-EBZ can not recognize the outer edge of the star at the position of 3 m and 2 m, respectively, as shown in Figure 31(l) and Figure 31(s).

Figure 31: Depth maps of Böhler star at different positions

Figure 32: Depth map of Azure Kinect at the distance of 2000 mm

As shown in Figure 32, P_1 and P_2 are the number of pixels occupied by the diameter of the ambiguous measured circle and the star, respectively. Then the lateral resolution can be calculated as:

$$r = \frac{\pi P_1 M}{n P_2} \quad (25)$$

The lateral resolution of every camera at different positions is shown in Figure 33. Theoretically, the maximum resolution this Böhler star can recognize is $r = \frac{\pi M}{n} = 26.18$ mm. However, when the resolution exceeds 20 mm, the outer edge of the star is not distinguished. For this reason, the upper limit of the lateral resolution is set to 20 mm. As shown in Figure 33, the lateral resolution of all cameras is kept below 10 mm within 1.4 m. It is remarkable that Helios2 with double modulation frequency has an overwhelming advantage over other cameras in terms of lateral resolution. It is kept below 6 mm even at a distance of 3 m. Similar to our observation of depth maps

in Figure 31, the lateral resolution of Azure Kinect and S100D has similar performance, and they increase approximately linearly with the increase of distance. L515 performs as well as Azure Kinect and S100D within 1.5 m. At 1.5 meters away, its resolution is slightly larger (lower) than theirs.

Figure 33: Lateral resolution at different distances

The angular resolution is calculated using equation (24) and the results are presented in Figure 34. In theory, angular resolution is approximately a fixed value. Like the camera of Azure Kinect, Helios2, and S100D cameras, they do not fluctuate largely with distance. However, the angular resolution of L515 at a distance greater than 1.5 meters is slightly larger than before. The lateral resolution of AD-96TOF1-EBZ has reached the upper limit set by us at 2.3 m, then after this distance, it shows a downward trend.

In fact, the theoretical angular resolution of every camera can be calculated according to the pixel resolution and FOV, as shown in Table 6. By comparison, we find that only the Helios2 is close to its theoretical value, while all other cameras are more than 2 times its theoretical value.

Figure 34: Angular resolution at different distances

Camera	Resolution	Field of View	Theoretical angular resolution
NFOV unbinned	640 × 576	75° × 65°	0.113°
Helios2	640 × 480	69° × 51°	0.106°
L515	640 × 480	70° × 55°	0.115°
S100D	640 × 480	60° × 45°	0.093°
AD-96TOF1-EBZ	640 × 480	90° × 69.2°	0.144°

Table 6: Theoretical angular resolution

5.4 Range resolution

In this experiment, three 5 cm×5 cm cuboids with different heights of 3.5, 7, and 14 mm, respectively, are used as test objects, as shown in Figure 35. The height of the whiteboard is zero relative to them. On the basis of the height difference between them and the whiteboard, the range resolution can be visualized.

Range resolution, or depth resolution, refers to the minimum reliably divisible distance in the unambiguous range. Based on the voltage resolution, which is defined as the ratio of total voltage swing and noise voltage generated by the storage capacitor, the range resolution R_r is defined as [4]:

$$R_r = \frac{c}{2f_m} \sqrt{\frac{P_{\text{laser}} + P_{\text{amb}}}{P_{\text{laser}}} \frac{A}{k_{\text{opt}} q_e r T}} \quad (26)$$

where c is the velocity of light, f_m is the modulation frequency. P_{laser} and P_{amb} are the power of illumination and ambient light, respectively. A is the total area illuminated. It also involves quantum efficiency q_e , reflectivity r , integration time T , and the constant parameter k_{opt} defined by the optical system.

Figure 35: Cuboids

Similar to the previous experiments, adjusting the camera to the target position from 0.5 m to 3 m, 10 cm an interval, the depth

data averaged by 30 frames are shown in Figure 36. To better compare depth measurements from different cameras, we can convert the depth maps recorded by S100D and AD-96TOF1-EBZ to the Z plane by using the compensation matrix, the results are shown in Figure 37.

It is observed from Figure 36 and Figure 37 that, for Azure Kinect and Helios2, the depth difference produced by the white panel and Cuboids with heights of 7 mm and 14 mm can be obviously observed. Furthermore, similar results can be observed with S100D after the compensation. The 3.5 mm depth difference is only observable for L515 at the distance of 0.6 and 1 m. Although the L515 has a standard deviation of less than 2 mm at 3 m, the lower lateral resolution leads to a more serious transition region at the edge of the cuboids, which in turn affects the depth information of the cuboids.

In fact, because of the smallest (highest) lateral resolution, only Helios2 exhibits a relatively narrow blurred region. With the increase of distance, the proportion of transition pixels between Cuboids increases, resulting in a relatively wider ambiguous border between cuboids.

As a result of the large standard deviation and low lateral resolution of AD-96TOF1-EBZ, the difference in the depth of the cuboids is not well distinguished at close range, and no further analysis of this will be done afterwards.

Figure 36: Depth maps of four-cuboid at different positions

Figure 37: Z plane depth maps of S100D and AD-96TOF1-EBZ after the compensation

With the purpose of exploring the range resolution level of each camera, we calculated the height difference between each cuboid and white panel at different distances, and the results are shown in Figure 38. We discarded pixels that were heavily affected by low lateral resolution in the calculation, and the depth information is averaged by 30 frames. Due to the high standard deviation and low angular resolution, AD-96TOF1-EBZ is not evaluated here.

It is observed from Figure 38(a) that L515 shows a significant downward trend after about 1.5 m. It is due to the influence of low lateral resolution and can not be avoided in the calculation process. Moreover, there is a slight downward trend in Azure Kinect and S100D at long distances, which is also for the same reason. Suppose that the effect of the low lateral resolution is ignored. The measurement error of all cameras for 14 mm height difference is kept within 3 mm. Considering the material error of 1 mm and the standard deviation of each camera, this error range is completely acceptable. The 7 mm height difference measurement is shown in Figure 38(b). All cameras show better performance, and the most errors are limited in the range of 2 mm when the influence of low lateral resolution on L515 is not considered. However, for a height difference of 3.5 mm, only the L515 in the range of 0.5 to 1.6 m has a relatively good performance, and the error is less than 1.5 mm, as shown in Figure

38(c).

(a) Cuboid with height of 14mm

(b) Cuboid with height of 7mm

(c) Cuboid with height of 3.5mm

Figure 38: Height difference between the cuboids and the white panel with the variation of distance

5.5 Multiple parameters visualization

In this experiment, a foam with a sinusoidal structure is measured, as shown in Figure 39. It features an amplitude of 2.5 cm and a wavelength of 4.5 cm. Owing to the complex shape of the sinusoidal structure, its depth imaging is affected by multiple parameters of cameras, such as precision, angular resolution, etc. Therefore, it can be regarded as a visualization tool for evaluating multiple parameters.

Figure 39: Sinusoidal structure

This experiment is also measured in the interval from 0.5 to 3 m with a step size of 10 cm. As can be seen from the results in Figure 40, only Azure Kinect and Helios2 can identify the peaks and troughs of the sinusoidal structure at the position of 2 m. For S100D, the peaks and valleys are displayed more clearly after the compensation matrix calibration, as shown in Figure 41(a) and Figure 41(b). For the depth images (h), (k), (l), (o), (p), and (t) in the Figure 40, the depth measurement values are far from the real distance. We adjust the depth observation range for these images to ensure that most of their depth information is within this range. Additionally, all the measured values of S100D at 3 m are invalid values of 0, as shown in Figure 40(p).

Figure 40: Depth maps of sinusoidal structure at different positions

Figure 41: Depth maps of sinusoidal structure from S100D and AD-96TOF1-EBZ after the calibration by the compensation matrix

For the sake of observing the imaging details of the surface of sinusoidal structure more clearly, the three-dimensional surface images are generated, as shown in Figure 42. The results seem a little surprising. Azure Kinect, L515, and S100D present a smoother surface image with a lower angular resolution. On the contrary, the surface image generated by Helios2, which owns the highest angular resolution, is sharper. In fact, as the angular resolution gets lower, the correlation between adjacent pixels gets stronger while making the depth transition between them better. For Helios2 with the higher angular resolution, the independence between adjacent pixels is stronger. Thus, the lower angular resolution results in smoother depth imaging of objects with curved surfaces to a certain extent. The original 3D surface maps for S100D as well as AD-96TOF1-EBZ are shown in Figure 43. In contrast, S100D has a good improvement after the compensation, but the improvement of AD-96TOF1-EBZ is not so good due to its poor precision, as shown in Figure 42(d) and Figure 42(e).

Figure 42: Three-dimensional surface of the sinusoidal structure at the distance of 1 m

Figure 43: Three-dimensional surface of the sinusoidal structure measured by S100D and AD-96TOF1-EBZ without compensation at the distance of 1 m

5.6 Flying pixels

In this experiment, we will observe the possible flying pixel phenomenon of each ToF camera at the edge of the whiteboard through the point cloud. The distance between the cameras and the white panel is adjusted to 1.5 meters. In order to avoid the contingency of one frame of the point cloud, we acquired five frames of point cloud images per camera and aligned them with the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm [47]. Before the alignment, the background of the point cloud is filtered by the PassThrough filter. It improves the speed of the alignment and avoids the uncertainty of sparse point clouds by the use of downsampling. In other words, the resulting point cloud contains 5 times the flying pixel noise of a single frame point cloud, which is shown in Figures 44-48. For S100 and AD-96TOF1-EBZ, the point clouds are generated by the distance maps. This causes the distance at the edge of the whiteboard to be larger than the center, as shown in Figures 47 and 48.

Where Figures (a) and (b) are point clouds of the white panel observed from the oblique rear and side perspectives, respectively. Combining observation from the two perspectives, we find that L515 has the slightest flying pixel noise near the whiteboard, as shown in Figure 46, which means L515 is more effective at detecting the edges of objects. Secondly, S100D has excellent performance as well, with only a few observable point cloud noise, as shown in Figure 47.

(a) 1.5m

(b) 1.5m

Figure 44: Point cloud of flying pixel phenomenon at the edge of the white panel recorded by Azure Kinect at the distance of 1.5 m

(a) 1.5m

(b) 1.5m

Figure 45: Point cloud of flying pixel phenomenon at the edge of the white panel recorded by Helios2 at the distance of 1.5 m

(a) 1.5m

(b) 1.5m

Figure 46: Point cloud of flying pixel phenomenon at the edge of the white panel recorded by L515 at the distance of 1.5 m

(a) 1.5m

(b) 1.5m

Figure 47: Point cloud of flying pixel phenomenon at the edge of the white panel recorded by S100D at the distance of 1.5 m

(a) 1.5m

(b) 1.5m

Figure 48: Point cloud of flying pixel phenomenon at the edge of the white panel recorded by AD-96TOF1-EBZ at the distance of 1.5 m

6 Conclusions

With the enhancement of ToF sensor pixel resolution to VGA level, more and more high-resolution cameras are flooding the market. To explore the performance of these cameras, we selected five state-of-the-art high-resolution cameras and evaluated their important parameters via six different experiments in this Thesis: 1) warm-up period, 2) accuracy and precision, 3) lateral resolution, 4) range resolution, 5) visualization of multiple parameters, and 6) flying pixel. The following conclusions are drawn.

1) It is worth noting that the S100D requires no waiting time to achieve stability after being powered up. Furthermore, the fluctuation of depth value is also kept within a small range of 1 mm. 2) The accuracy variation of Azure Kinect, Helios2, and L515 at the range from 0.5 to 3 m is kept within 6 mm. In addition, at the same measurement range, the standard deviation is kept below 2mm. 3) The angular resolution of Helios2 can reach its theoretical value of 0.106° within the measurement range. 4) Within the range of 1.5 m, the depth resolution of L515 can reach 3.5 mm. 5) L515, S100D, and Azure Kinect, whose angular resolution does not reach its theoretical value, show a more smooth surface for sinusoidal structure. 6) At the distance of 1.5 m, there is little flying pixel noise in the point cloud of the white panel recorded by L515.

Future research may include evaluating the performance dependency on different incident angles, motion artifacts, MPI, and each camera's 3D reconstruction.

Appendix A Point cloud of the white panel

Figures 44(b), 45(b), and 46(b) present the point cloud from the side perspective of Azure Kinect, Helios2, and L515, respectively. L515 shows a larger range in the Z direction than the other two cameras, namely the thickness of the point cloud corresponding to the white panel. Since they used the same ICP algorithm for registration, we speculated that it was due to the large dispersion degree of the point cloud generated by L515. To verify this conjecture and avoid the influence of the ICP algorithm, we will observe the point cloud plane generated by a frame of the white panel, as shown in Figures 49-51. For a clearer view of the surface details, we darken the point cloud background. It is observed that the point cloud planes generated by Azure Kinect and Helios2 are finer than L515, as we have speculated.

Figure 49: A frame of point cloud for white panel generated by Azure Kinect at the distance of 1.5 m

Figure 50: A frame of point cloud for white panel generated by Helios2 at the distance of 1.5 m

Figure 51: A frame of point cloud for white panel generated by L515 at the distance of 1.5 m

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